

**FOLIO FROM MANUSCRIPT A DIVAN OF MIR "ALI SHIR NAVAI "IN SILK ROAD
INTERNATIONAL UNIVERSITY TOURISM AND CULTURAL HERITAGE
(ARTISTIC STUDY AND TO BE PUBLISHED FOR THE FIRST TIME)**

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Abstract. Diwan Al-Nawa'i or Ali Shir Navai (16 century) one of the most famous manuscripts dating back to Alisher Nawai and one of the most famous literary manuscripts in East Asia. Many libraries have copies of this Diwan, This research is unique in publishing copy a manuscript paper from this Diwan preserved at the International Silk Road University, And studying it, as well as introducing the manuscript, the Diwan, and its author, Alishir al-Nawawi, who is considered the founder of Turkish (ancient Uzbek) literature and the first to set its rules, so scholars followed his approach, using his vocabulary and words. And studying the various artistic elements that appeared in this manuscript and the various influences. - this research is important for the archaeological dimension in studying the manuscript in the authors copy from the archaeological point of view ,considering that is in itself an inscribed artefact.

This research will show the archaeological indicators and features of manuscript ,saved in the silk road international university subject of study ,In the context of what was mentioned in the sources about the methodology from copying books .

Identifying a new version and its importance, highlighting the artistic elements it contains artistic and aesthetic values and learning about the design that uses colours drawings, etc

Keywords: Manuscript, Diwan Al-Nawa'i, Diwan ali shir navai, Altemurin, Herat, Motifs

Figure 1 : Folio from Manuscript a Divan of Mir "Ali Shir Navai "in

Silk Road International University tourism and cultural heritage, Published for the first time.

Figure 2: First page of the study manuscript " Diwan Al-Nawa'i"

Figure 3: Second page of manuscript Diwan Al-Nawa'i"

Figure 4:
decoration in the
cross ,

4:

Geometric

Figure 5: Detailed
decoration

5: Detailed

floral

Figure 6: Decoration for a
flower

Figure 7: Decoration of a floral ribbon interspersed with flowers

Figure 8: Transcribing the writings that appeared on the study manuscript, Researcher's work

Figure 9: Transcribing of another part of the writings that appeared on the study manuscript ,
Researcher's work

Figure 10: A transcription of a floral decoration that appeared on the manuscript of the study, Researcher's work

Figure 11: A transcription of a cross-shaped decoration that appeared on the manuscript of the study, Researcher's work

Figure 12: Shapes of the Byzantine cross , according to, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Christian_cross_variants

Figure 13: A transcription of a floral decoration that appeared on the manuscript of the study, Researcher's work